

High-vertical resolution sampling reveals sharp Thin Layers of Toxic Phytoplankton in the Patagonian Fjords, Southern Chile

Fig. 1. Map of the study area showing: (A) Northern Chilean Patagonia inland sea (the black box delimits the Puyuhuapi fjord), and (B) The study area and sampling stations (red circles) in Puyuhuapi fjord.

Thin layers of phytoplankton (TLP) are narrow (a few cm to less than 5m) bands of water where aggregated cells and their pigments may reach biomass levels (chlorophyll *a*, cell densities) several orders of magnitude higher than the layers immediately above or below [1]. These layers are the result of complex interactions between physical (vertical gradients in density and water velocity) and biological (swimming, buoyancy control, behaviour) processes and are ecologically significant. TLPs act as microenvironments where biological activity is enhanced, influencing processes such as primary productivity, trophic web transfers and the accumulation of bioactive compounds—including both particulate and dissolved shellfish toxins [2].

Thin Layers of toxin-producing microalgae may also act as a “toxic carpet”, posing a significant threat to caged-fish and to bivalves cultivated on long lines and suspended rafts [3]. TLPs often arise from a “stretched” subsurface chlorophyll maximum and may go undetected when only conventional bottle sampling at fixed

depth intervals—or worse, only surface waters collected with a bucket—are collected in the framework of HAB monitoring programmes [4]. Here, we describe TLPs formed by two lipophilic toxin producers, *Dinophysis acuminata* and *Dinophysis acuta*, and their associated toxins in the southern Chilean fjords. These *Dinophysis* species are known to produce two kinds of toxins: Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxins (DST: okadaic acid, OA, and Dinophysistoxins, DTXs) and Pectenotoxins (PTXs) [5]. The diarrhetic toxins are bioaccumulated by mussels and other filter feeders, which act as vectors, transferring them through the food web. Consumers of contaminated shellfish may suffer from the diarrhetic shellfish poisoning syndrome. To protect public health, shellfish harvesting is prohibited whenever toxin levels in the shellfish meat exceed regulatory thresholds, leading to significant economic losses for the shellfish industry. Furthermore, harmful effects of both DSTs and PTXs—whether particulate or dissolved—on larval stages of molluscs, crustaceans and fish, have been demonstrated

under laboratory conditions. However, their impact on the recruitment of commercially important species in the wild remains poorly understood [6-7].

The Patagonian fjords, characterised by permanent strong salinity gradients, high water residence times, and estuarine-like circulation patterns, provide optimal conditions for the formation and persistence of TLPs [8]. Describing the physical and chemical characteristics of these microstructures is crucial for understanding the optimal species (strain)-specific conditions that favour growth and toxin production. This knowledge is key to enhancing early warning systems and predictive models.

In 23 November 2023, a survey was carried out in Puyuhuapi fjord (Fig. 1A), off Puerto Cisnes (Fig. 1B) to compare vertical profiles of *Dinophysis* species obtained through conventional methods (Niskin bottles sampled every 2 m) with those from a high vertical resolution sampler (MAR = muestreador de alta resolución) (Fig. 2). This sampling device, made in Chile, was inspired by the Fine-Scale Sampler

(FSS) developed at Ifremer [9]. The Chilean MAR, adapted to sample the narrow mixed layer (around 10m) and sharp haloclines in the fjords, consists of a 2 m high by 38.5 cm wide rectangular frame, fitted with eight 1.7 L Niskin bottles spaced 25 cm apart. CTD (Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth) casts from the surface to 20 m depth were used to determine, in real time, the vertical distribution of temperature, salinity, and *in vivo* *Chl a* fluorescence (F)—key parameters for tracking the position and characteristics (depth, width, intensity) of the TLP. The CTD data were processed and visualized using RStudio software.

For the quantitative analysis of *Dinophysis* species, 100ml aliquots from each conventional bottle (0–20 m every 4m) and MAR sample, were transferred to UV-protected, screw-cap glass jars and immediately fixed with Lugol's

solution. Between 10 and 25 mL of each fixed sample were allowed to sediment overnight in Utermöhl chambers, and large *Dinophysis* cells were counted using an Olympus CX40 inverted microscope at 100× magnification (detection limit: 40–100 cells·L⁻¹).

For analysis of lipophilic toxins, 1 L aliquots from each bottle were filtered through Whatman GF/F fibreglass filters (47 mm, 0,7 µm pore size). The filters were stored in cryotubes and sent to the analytical chemistry laboratory for lipophilic toxin analysis, following protocols described in [10].

Throughout the sampling campaign, the fjord exhibited a strong haline stratification in the top 5 m (Fig. 3A). Water temperature ranged from 11 to 10 °C, with a minimum of 9 °C at 1–2 m depth. A pronounced salinity gradient (5 to 25 PSU) was observed between 5 and 15 m—typical mid-spring conditions in

Puyuhuapi Fjord, attributed to heavy freshwater discharge from the Cisnes River following snowmelt [11]. The CTD fluorescence sensor detected a sharp chlorophyll fluorescence maximum equivalent to 46.6 µg·L⁻¹ *Chl a* at a depth of 4.8 m (Fig. 3A), meeting the criteria proposed by Dekshenieks et al. [1] for defining a thin layer.

Marked differences were observed between the cell density profiles derived from conventional and MAR sampling (Fig. 3B). Conventional methods detected a maximum density of *D. acuminata* of 4,000 cells·L⁻¹ at 4 m—coinciding with peaks in OA (1.9 ng·mL⁻¹) and PTX2 (14.4 ng·mL⁻¹)—and a *D. acuta* cell maximum (200 cells·L⁻¹) at 6 m, i.e., 2 m above the DTX1 maximum (0,1 ng·mL⁻¹) (Fig. 3B). In contrast, MEF sampling revealed a five-fold higher *D. acuminata* density (20,800 cells·L⁻¹) at 4 m, with correspondingly higher OA (4.7 ng·mL⁻¹), DTX1 (0.1 ng·mL⁻¹), and PTX2 (25 ng·mL⁻¹) concentrations (Fig. 3C). A shift in toxin distribution was also detected, with the toxin peak at 4.5 m coinciding with a *D. acuta* maximum of 900 cells·L⁻¹. The results presented here show that the MAR provides enhanced resolution for detecting the vertical distribution of *Dinophysis* species and their associated toxins. It also enables a more accurate estimation of the real magnitude of the toxic dinoflagellate population—critical for estimating division rates and other key ecological parameters. In summary, high-vertical resolution sampling yields more realistic information on the spatial distribution and physiological status of target species. Such strategies are particularly important in strongly stratified systems like the Chilean fjords, which host both valuable aquaculture operations and protected nature reserves and are increasingly exposed to various harmful algal bloom events—including shellfish toxin producers, fish-killing species, and high-biomass nuisance blooms [6].

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Fig. 2. Fine scale sampler (Mar = Muestreador de Alta Resolución) a sampling device with a vertical resolution of 25 cm. (A) A fin providing stability to the structure submerged in the water, (B) Skeleton of the structure where the (C) Eight Niskin bottles of 1.7 L are positioned.

Fig. 3. (A) Vertical profiles of temperature, salinity, and chlorophyll concentration. The gray-shaded area indicates the range where samples were collected using the MAR (3–5 m). (B) Vertical distribution of *Dinophysis acuta* and *Dinophysis acuminata* (0–20 meters) along with the vertical distribution of their associated lipophilic toxins. The gray-shaded area indicates the MAR sampling depth interval (3–5 m). (C) High-resolution vertical distribution of *Dinophysis* species and their lipophilic toxins between 3–5 meters.

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Fig. 4. Preparing the high vertical resolution profiler before sampling. Puyuhuapi Fjord, Aysén, Chile, 2025.